

Ethno-Botanical Survey of Plants used to Treat *Diabetes Milletus* in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja FCT, Nigeria

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Abstract: *Diabetes is an extremely serious public health issue. In light of this, the primary goal of this study is to identify the plants used in diabetes treatment, and to characterize the therapeutic applications of these plants using ethnobotanical data collected in Gwagwalada area council. This survey was carried out using oral interview and semi-structured questionnaires. These were administered to forty-eight respondents which is made up of Traditional Medical Practitioners (TMPS), herb sellers, civil servants, and farmers. The result showed that a total of forty-one plant species belonging to thirty-five genera and thirty-two families were found to be useful in the treatment of DM. The plants with the highest frequency of citation in management of DM include *Veronia amygdalina*(16%), *Moringa oleifera*(10%), citrus lemon (9%), and *Ocimum gratissimum*(8%). Decoction (38%) and infusion (23%) were the main method of preparation while the main route of administration is oral. The leaf is the major part of plant used in herbal preparation.*

Keywords: *Ethnobotanical, Federal Capital Territory, Diabetes, Medicinal plants, Survey, Management*

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1.0 Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a disease associated with high blood sugar level because of defective carbohydrate and lipid metabolism which affect the body utilization of insulin (Samuel *et al.*, 2018). Insulin helps the conversion of glucose to energy and its activity is truncated resulting in damage of vital organs due to hyperglycemia and glucose toxicity. Untreated cases of the disease result in long standing complications such as kidney failure, heart disease, stroke, foot ulcers, and damage to the eyes (Singab *et al.*, 2014.)

Globally the number of people with diabetes has risen from 108 million to 422 million in 2014 (Mathers, 2002) and the disease currently caused 1.6 million deaths in 2015 (Roglic *et al.*, 2018). In addition, it has been predicted that the number of diabetic patients will increase to 300 million by 2025 (Williams, 2003). The world health organization projects that diabetes will be the seventh leading cause of death in 2023 (Mathers, 2002).

The problem of diabetes mellitus is increasing at world level. It is common for both genders i.e male and female (Bhatwa, *et al.*, 2021). The main factors responsible for this worldwide

problem are genetic disorder, behavioral and environmental risk factors. Modifiable risk factors such as obesity and physical inactivity are the main non-genetic determinants of diabetes (Arshpreet *et al.*, 2015).

Diabetes mellitus is associated with some other pathogenic processes. It starts with the destruction of beta cells of the pancreas by autoimmune disease causing low secretion of insulin from beta cells of pancreas and desensitization of receptors responsible for the action of insulin. As a result of the above abnormalities in insulin, the normal metabolic process of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates become disturbed American Diabetes Association, (2010). The American Diabetes Association further explained the two types of diabetes mellitus. i.e. *Diabetes mellitus 1* and *Diabetes mellitus 2*

In *Diabetes mellitus 1*, the beta cells fail to produce insulin. Due to the low level of insulin, the body's level of glucose increased in the body which is the main cause of diabetes mellitus. Type 1 Diabetes accounts for approximately 5%-10% of all cases of the disease. (Kadiri, 2015). Type 1 diabetes typically develops in children aged 4 years and older, and the peak incidence in

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children of 11 and 13 years Kadiri(2015). Some cases of type 1 diabetes occur in adults, and cases of type 1 have been reported in people in the 8th and 9th decade of life.

In *Diabetes mellitus 2*, the body fails to utilize insulin. Due to improper use of insulin, the level of glucose decreased in the body which is the main cause of diabetes mellitus. Type 2 Diabetes accounts for approximately 90%-95% of all cases of the disease (Kadiri, 2011). The second category of diabetes named as Type 2 diabetes (T2D) is the most prevalent form that develops due to the combined action of both insulin resistance and insufficient insulin secretion.

However, there are many other types of diabetes (gestational, drug- induced, infection - induced or disease - induced etc). There is also a condition called pre-diabetes. Pre-diabetes is a condition in which the Hba, C, D plasma glucose and other markers of diabetes are persistently elevated but are not high enough to require treatment. People with pre-diabetes have an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes, heart disease and stroke. T2D cannot be completely cured but its severity and symptoms can be managed by the use of drugs and lifestyle modifications. Some of the most commonly used pharmacological agents for the treatment of T2D include drugs from different classes such as biguanides (ex. metformin), sulfonylureas (glyburide and glipizide), meglitinides (ex. repaglinide and nateglinides) and thiazolidinediones (pioglitazone). The drugs belonging to these classes are administered as the first line of defense to prevent deterioration of the diabetic state (Bhatwa *et al.*, 2021).

According to Adeniran *et al.*, (2020), ethnobotanical knowledge is traditionally passed on verbally from generation to generation within the FCT, and as such practitioners depend entirely on memory for their practice. This mode of knowledge transfer may lead to interrupted knowledge transmission; intergenerational knowledge erosion and its effect are discrepancies between knowledge and actual use of medicinal plants (Adeniran *et al.*, 2020).

In order to preserve this sensitive knowledge, medicinal plants must be documented. Therefore, documentation and digitalization of our indigenous knowledge of traditional medicine will ensure the permanent preservation of the wealthy knowledge of the use of the medicinal

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plant for the management of various ailments (Adeniran *et al.*, 2020). Also, in our quest for the search for new drugs, it is of great importance to document indigenous traditional knowledge about medicinal plants before they disappear due to climate change, land use and plant overexploitation (Adeniran *et al.*, 2020).

The currently available modern medicines used for diabetes management which include insulin injections and oral hypoglycemic agents have not been able to cure the disease while causing adverse side effects and complications to the patients after prolonged use (Al-Rubeaan, *et al.*, 2020). Due to these limitations, anti-diabetic drug discovery has shifted its focus to medicinal plants as alternative sources of new anti-diabetics. Based on traditional medicine information, diabetes has been treated with herbs and medicinal plants for a long time (Rahimi *et al.*, 2017). However, most of the available ethno-medical information regarding the anti-diabetic potential of these plants is not provided with scientific data (Rahimi *et al.*, 2015), Few of them have undergone scientific and medical evaluation to assess their anti-diabetic efficacy (Dowarah and Singh 2020; Rahimy *et al.*, 2017), The few scientific evaluated medicinal plants reported to show antidiabetic potential were shown to have useful active phytochemical compounds which include terpenoids, alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides (Bagri *et al.*, 2016).

A recent survey has revealed that 35 to 4% of diabetic patients use complementary and alternative medicines (mostly botanicals) in addition to conventional medicine, (Kifle, 2021). However, there has been increasing demand for the use of plant products with anti diabetic activity due to low cost, easy availability, abundance and lesser side effects. Plant materials are continuously scrutinized and explored for their effect as hypoglycemic agents (Kifle, 2021). The objective of the present study was to identify some plants used in the treatments of diabetes and this study was also carried out to document ethnobotanical information of indigenous plants used to manage of diabetes mellitus in FCT. The aim of this survey is to prevent over exploitation of medicinal plants, and for digitalization, also to provide a baseline data for future scientists to leverage on.

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2.0 Materials and Method**2.1 The Study Area**

Abuja, Nigeria's capital city is located in the center of the country. The Federal Capital Territory (FCT) has a land area of 8,000 square kilometers which is two and half times the size of Lagos, the former capital of Nigeria (FCDA). It lies between latitude 8°25N & 9°20 and longitude 6°39. The FCT is divided into six area councils: kuje, Municipal, Gwagwalada, Abaji, Bwari and Kwali (FCDA).

2.2 Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained orally from all respondents made up of Traditional Medical Practitioners (TMPS), herb sellers, civil servants and farmers before inception of the interview.

3.0 Administration of questionnaires

Ethnobotanical information on the plants used in the management of Diabetes mellitus was obtained by consulting Traditional Medical Practitioners (TMP) and herb sellers. The use of semi-structured questionnaire and oral interview were adopted to obtain the relevant Ethnobotanical data. The questionnaires were administered by trained interviewers and in some cases, monetary incentives were given to unwilling respondents. It was divided into two sections:

Section (A) dealt with demographic information such as age, sex, religion, marital status, educational background, tribe and working experience.

Section (B) was one professional experiences of plants used in management of *Diabetes Mellitus*.

3.1 Collection and authentication of plant samples

Fresh plant samples were collected from Traditional Medical Practitioners (TMPS), herb sellers, civil servants and farmers. Herbal remedies were authenticated by comparison with appropriate voucher specimens at the herbaria in the Department of Biological Sciences, University of Abuja.

4.0 Results and Discussion**4.1 Result**

The study area (Gwagwalada) comprises of ten towns in Gwagwalada area council in Federal Capital Territory, these include: Zuba, Ibwa, Dobi, Kutunku, Tungamaje, Paikon Kore, Ikwa,

Gwako, Quarters, and Central and Giri. Forty-eight (48) questionnaires were administered in ten major towns in Gwagwalada Area Council.

In this study, 41 medicinal plants are used for the management of diabetes. These include *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Citrus lemon*, *Abelmoschus esculentus* *Calotropis procera*, *Vernonia amygdalina*, *Musa Citrullus colocynthis*, *longi pedunculata*, *Gladiolus dalenii* Van.Geel, *Curculigo piliosaq*, *Aristolochia rigens*, *Picralima nitida*, *Vernonia amygalina*, *Petivera allicea* *Citrullus colocythis* and *Gongrolema latifolium* Benth, *M.oleifera*, *O.gratissimum*, *Alium sativum*, *Musa parasidica* etc

Among all the identified plants, *M. oleifera* and *V. amygalina* are the most commonly used plants by the FCT residents to treat *Diabetes mellitus*. Thirty-two (32) families were identified. Most of the plants belong to the family Asteraceae (17%) of the total plants identified, followed by Moringaceae (10%), *Rutaceae* (9%) and *Ocimum gratissimum* (8%).

4.2 Demographical Survey of Respondents

Informants were mainly Muslims 63% from Yoruba ethnic group in Nigeria and Christians 38% and their educational background include primary 15%, secondary 54%, Tertiary 31%. All the informants were married (100%). 63% of the informants were men while 38% were women as shown in table 1. The informants that were Hausa are 6/48 (13%), 2/48(4%) Igbo, 29/48(60%) were Yoruba, 2/48(2%) were Fulani while 10/48(20%) were others (Idoma, Tiv and Ibibio) as shown in table 1.

4.3 Discussion

In this study, 41 medicinal plants are used for the management of diabetes. These include *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Citrus lemon*, *Abelmoschus esculentus* *Calotropis procera*, *Vernonia amygdalina*, *Musa Citrullus colocynthis*, *Securidaca long ipedunculata*, *Gladiolus dalenii* Van.Geel, *Curculigo piliosaq*, *Aristolochia rigens*, *Picralima nitida*, *Vernonia amygalina*, *Petivera allicea* *Citrullus colocythis* and *Gongrolema latifolium* Benth, *M.oleifera*, *O.gratissimum*, *Alium.sativum*, *Musa parasidica*etc. This is in agreement with the work done by Kadiri *et al.*, (2015).

Among all the identified plants, *M. oleifera* and *V. amygalina* are the most commonly used plants by the FCT residents to treat *Diabetes mellitus*.

The result in revealed that the families with the highest occurrence of species is Asteraceae. This is in line with the findings of Kadiri *et al.*, (2015) which is an indicative of their importance in the treatment of *Diabetes mellitus*.

The frequent occurrence of other families also suggests their importance as repository of useful plants which may be explored for treatment of diabetes and other diseases.

In table 1, the result showed that young people between the age of (41-50 years) are more involved in the practice of traditional herbal medicines.

This is contrary to the findings of Faleyemi and Oluwana (2008) who reported that the older the people, the more active and experience they are in the use and sourcing of medicinal plants. This could also be as a result of high involvement in traditional medicine as a primary occupation by the young people, Mustaph *et al.*, (2014).

Religion	Christianity	38
	Islam	63
Tribe	Hausa	13
	Igbo	4
	Yoruba	60
	Fulani	2
	Others	20

KEY: H(Hausa) ; F (Fulani) ; Y(Yoruba) ; I (Igbo) ; O(Others)

The informants that were Hausa are 6/48 (13%), 2/48(4%) Igbo, 29/48(60%) were Yoruba, 2/48(2%) were Fulani while 10/48(20%) were others (Idoma, Tiv and Ibibio) as shown in table 1.

The result in Table 1 shows that larger percentages of respondents were males. This is in agreement with the work of Kadiri *et al.*, (2015). This could be an indication that males are more involved in herbal practices than their counterpart.

In Table 1 the result showed that most of the respondents are educated with Secondary school certificate. This agrees with the work done by Kadiri *et al.*, (2015). The basic education attainment may enhance the respondents the necessary proficiency needed for documentation and digitalization.

Table 1: The Respondent Distribution

Sex	Female/Male	38-63
Age group (year)	20 – 30	...
	31 – 40	25
	41 – 50	42
	51 – 60	29
	60 and above	4
Education	Primary	15
	Secondary	54
	Tertiary	31
	None	--
Marital Status	Married	100
	Single	---
	Divorced	---
Worked Experience	1 – 5	21
	6 – 10	27
	11 – 15	15
	16 – 20	21

The Age Group of the Respondents : 25% of the informants fall within the range of 30 - 40 years, 42% of the informants fall within the range of 41-50 years, 29% of the informants fall within the range of 51-60 years and 4% of the informants fall within the range of 60 years and above as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The different age groups of the respondents in years

The result in Figure 4 shows that the leaves formed the most frequently used parts. This agrees with the work of Mustapha, (2014). This could be attributed to the leaves being the major

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sites in deposition of plant secondary metabolites.

secondary), this shows that, they have the ability to adopt to new innovations techniques.

Figure 3 shows that most of the plants part is prepared using decoction method. This could be attributed to the higher extraction of constituents using hot water.

However, the result in table 1 shows that there is no graduate in the studied populations could be as a result that graduates are not interested in traditional herbal practices and it may be because of the low-income rate. The working experience between 6 and 10 years was highest (27%) which

4.4 The mode of administration is via oral. Analysis of the demographic data (Table 1) confirmed all the respondents were married and are Muslims. Majority of the respondents were males. This is in line with the belief that men should fend for the family. The educational qualification of the respondents is high (54% for

reveals adequate knowledge of traditional herbal practices.

TABLE 2: The Different Towns and The Plants Recommended

S/N	Town	Plants Recommended
1	Dobi	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> , <i>Citrus lemon</i> and <i>Abelmoschus Esculentus</i>
2	Ikwa	<i>Calotropis procera</i> , <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> , <i>Musa paradisiaca</i> , and <i>Thaumatococcus dan.</i>
3	Ibwa	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> , <i>Securid ca long ipedunculata</i> , <i>Gladiolus dalenii</i> Van. Geel, <i>Curculigo piliosa</i> , <i>Aristolochia rigens</i> , <i>Picralima nitida</i> , <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> , <i>Petivera allicea</i> <i>Citrullus colocythis</i> and citrus
4	Zuba	<i>corea Dumetorum</i> , <i>Citrus lemon</i> , <i>Corchorus olitorius</i> , <i>ium sativum Murraykoenigii</i> (L), <i>Luffa aegyptiaca</i> and <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> .
5	Paikon Kore	<i>nonia. amygdalina</i> Delile, <i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> , <i>Allium sativum</i> and <i>Citrus lemon</i> .
6	Tumgamaje	<i>Vernonia. amygdalina</i> , <i>Curcuma longa</i> <i>Anisopus manni</i> , <i>Moringa oleifera</i> , <i>Allium sativum</i> , <i>Allium cepa</i> and <i>Zea mays</i>
7	Gwako	<i>Allium palliumsativum</i> , <i>Viscum flavescens</i> , <i>Ocimum tissimum</i> , <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> , <i>Moringa oleifera</i> and <i>Azadirachta indica</i> .
8	Quarters & Central	<i>Ficus exasperata</i> vahl, <i>Viscum album</i> linn, <i>Persea americana</i> , <i>O. gratissimum</i> , and <i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> .
9	Giri	<i>cus nucifera</i> , <i>Luffa aegyptiaca</i> , <i>Allium sativum</i> , <i>Citrus rantifolia</i> , <i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> , <i>Khaya ivorensis</i> , and <i>V. amygdalina</i> .
10	Kutunku	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> , <i>Garcinia kola</i> , <i>Moringa oleifera</i> , <i>Citrullus lanatus</i> , <i>Heteropogon contortus</i> , <i>Gongronema Latifolium</i> and <i>Apocynum</i>

KEY: H(Hausa) ; F (Fulani) ; Y(Yoruba) ; I (Igbo) ; O(Others).

Table 3: The list of most commonly anti-diabetic plants found in Gwagwalada Area Council, FCT Abuja.

S/N	Family	Botanical Name	Common Name	Local Name	Part used	Freq	Percent
1.	Alliaceae	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	Onions	Alubasa	Bulb	2	2.5
2.	Apocynaceae	<i>Picralima nitida</i> (Stapf) Durand and H. Durand 2	T. Picralima	Abeere (Y)	Seed	1	1.25
3.	Apocynaceae	<i>Anisopus mannii</i> N.E.Br		Kasha zaki	Stem	1	1.25
4.	Arecaceae	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Coco nut	Agbon (Y)	Bark	1	1.25
5.	Aristoloniaceae	<i>Aristolochia rigens</i> Vahl	Pelican flower	Akogu (y)	Root	1	1.25
6.	Asclepiadaceae	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton)Dryland	Sodom apple/giantmilk weed	Eweibomubomu (Y)	Leaf	1	1.25
7.	Asclepiadaceae	<i>Secamon afzeli</i>		Eweailu (Y)	Leaf	1	1.25
8.	Asclepiadaceae	<i>Gongronema latifolium</i> Benth	Bush buck	Utazi (I)	Leaf	1	1.25
9.	Asteraceae	<i>Venonia amygdalina</i> Delile	Bitter leaf	Awuro (Y)	Leaf	12	20
10.	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	African cucumba	Ewe ejiriri (Y)	Fruit	1	1.25
11.	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Citruslus colocynthis</i> (L.)Schrad	Bitter Apple	Bara (Y)	Bark	1	2.5
12.	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Luffa aegyptiaca</i> Mill.	Bitter apple	Bara (Y)	Fruit	2	2.5
13.	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Citrullus Lonatus</i> (Thumb)	Water melon	Kalahari (H)	Fruit/seed	1	1.25
14.	Dioscoreaceae	<i>Dioscorea dumetorum</i> (Kunth)Pax	Bitter yam	Esuru (Y)	Root	1	1.25
15.	DogbanesorApocynaceae	<i>Apocynum cannabinum</i> Lour	India hemp		Seed	1	1.25
16.	Guttiferae	<i>Garcinia afzelii</i> Engl.	Bitter kola	Orogbo (Y)	Seed	1	1.25
17.	Hypoxidaceae	<i>Curculigo pilosa</i> (Schum andthorn)	Schumach and Thorn	Ipakun (Y)	Root	1	1.25
18.	Iridaceae	<i>Gladiolus daleniivan</i> .Gel	African Gladiolus	Baka (Y)	Root	1	1.25
19.	Lamiaceae	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> forsski	scent leaf	Ayu (Y)	Leaf	6	7.5
20.	Lamiaceae	<i>Ocimumbasillicum</i> L.	Sweet basil	Efirri (Y)	Leaf	1	1.25
21.	Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Avocado pear	Ipia (Y)	Leaf	1	1.25
22.	Liliaceae	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Garlic	Efirin (Y)	Bulb	6	7.5
23.	Loranthaceae	<i>Viscum album</i> linn	Afomo		Leaf	2	2.5
24.	Malvaceae	<i>Abelmoschuseculentus</i> (L.) Moench	Okra	Kubewa (H)	Seed	1	1.25
25.	Marantaceae	<i>Thaumatococcusdaniellii</i> (Benn.) Benth	Miracle fruit	Ekoogbona	Leaf	1	1.25
26.	Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss	Neem	Dogoyaro (H)	Leaf	3	3.75
27.	Meliaceae	<i>Khayaivorensis</i> A. Chev.	Mahogany		Bark	1	1.25
28.	Moraceae	<i>Ficusexasperata</i> Vahl	Sand peper leaf	Ipin (Y)	Leaf	1	1.25
29.	Moringaceae	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Drum stick	Zogole (H)	Root	8	12.5
30.	Petiveriaceae	<i>Petiveraallicea</i>		Awogba	Stem	1	1.25
31.	Plantaginaceae	<i>Musa pradisiciaca</i> L.	Unripe plantain	Ogedeagba (Y)	Fruit	1	1.25
32.	Poaceae	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC.)Stapf	Lemon grass		Leaf	1	1.25
33.	Poaceae	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Var	Spear grass	Ipeh (I)	Root	1	1.25

		contours					
34.	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize spong	Masara (H)	Flower	1	1.25
35.	Polygalaceae	<i>Securidaca Longi pedunculata</i> Fre	Violet tree	Ipeta (Y)	Root	1	1.25
36.	Rutaceae	<i>Citrus lemon</i> (L.)	Lime	Osanwewe (Y)	Fruit	6	7.5
37.	Rutaceae	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.) Spreng	Curry leaf		Leaf	1	1.25
38.	Rutaceae	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	Lime	Lemutsami (H)	Fruit	1	1.25
39.	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum incanum</i>	Bitter apple	Gauta (H)	Fruit	1	1.25
40.	Tiliaceae	<i>Corchorus olitorius</i>	Jute	Ayoyo (H)	Seed	1	1.25
41.	Zingiberaceae	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Tumeric	Chita (H)	Root	1	1.25

KEY: H(Hausa) ; F (Fulani) ; Y(Yoruba) ; I (igbo) ; O(Others)

Figure 2: The most commonly mentioned plant used in the management of *D.mellitus* in Gwagwalada Area Council Abuja

Methods of Anti diabetic plants preparation

The mode of preparation of surveyed anti-diabetic plants: Most of the plants (38%) are prepared as decoction followed by infusion (23%), tea (22%) and alcoholic extract (17%) as shown in figure 2. The decoctions are used mostly because of the belief that hot water extracts more constituents.

Percentages

Figure 3: The mode of preparation of medicinal plants used in the management of diabetes mellitus in FCT, Abuja

The plant parts used for the management of Diabetes Mellitus in FCT, Abuja

The plant part used for the management of *D. mellitus* in Gwagwalada Area Council include root 22.4%, stem 4.1%, leaf 30.6%, whole plant 4.1%, fruit 10.2%, seed 12.2%, flower 2%, bark 10.2%, and bulb 4.1% as shown in figure.3. The leaf is the part that is commonly used in the management of

D. mellitus followed by root. The use of the leaves could be attributed to easy availability and also due to the presence of high number of chemical compounds which could be easily extracted and used in different forms. Imram *et al.* (2014). Leaves are the most commonly used plant's part by the traditional healers. Ngbolua *et al.* (2014).

Figure 4: The plant parts used for the management of Diabetes Mellitus in FCT, Abuja.

5.0 Conclusion

In this survey, 41 medicinal plant species are used by the FCT residents in the management of *D. mellitus*. Various plant species were identified and the most frequently used medicinal plant species are *Vernonia amygalina* and *Moringa oleifera*. The mode of preparation of anti-diabetic plants is decoction and the part that is frequently used is the leaf. In table 1, the result showed that quadragenarian between the age of (41-50 years)

are more involved in the practice of traditional herbal medicines.

Recommendations

Diabetes mellitus is a serious threat to the growing population of Nigeria especially people living in the urban areas. Affordable and accessible management of the diseases should be advocated. Effort on isolation and elucidation of bioactive materials in the plants should be

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encouraged. Digitalization of the botanicals should also be encouraged by researchers to avoid knowledge erosion.

Conflict of interest

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Author Contribution

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